

Prevalence of Invasive candidiasis in Blood stream infection in ICU patients of A Multi-Speciality Hospital, Gujarat

Vasava H¹, Mehta V², Tadvi M³, Chandpara P⁴

¹Third Year PG Resident, Department of Microbiology, Parul Institute of Medical Sciences & Research, Parul University, Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

²Professor & Head, Department of Microbiology, Parul Institute of Medical Sciences & Research, Parul University, Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

³Third Year PG Resident, Department of Microbiology, Parul Institute of Medical Sciences & Research, Parul University, Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

⁴Second Year PG Resident, Department of Microbiology, Parul Institute of Medical Sciences & Research, Parul University, Vadodara, Gujarat, India

Received: 25-08-2024 / Revised: 23-09-2024 / Accepted: 26-10-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Himanshu Vasava

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Invasive candidiasis is a fungal disease caused by *Candida* spp. that affects internal organs through blood stream infections. It's a major concern in hospitals, accounting for 96% of opportunistic mycoses. *Candida* infections occur due to interplay between fungal virulence and host immune responses. India's estimated annual incidence of candidemia is 4,70,000 cases, with *Candida tropicalis*, *Candida albicans*, and *Candida auris* being major contributors.

Methodology: A laboratory based retrospective analytic study was conducted over period 2-year (May 2022 - April 2024). The blood culture bottles were processed in Microbiology Laboratory, using BACT/ALERT 3D machine for 5-day aerobic incubation, identification of *Candida* spp was done by Gram stain, culture on SDA, Germ tube test and subspecies conformation *Candida* Chromogenic media used, further identification and antifungal susceptibility testing was done by VITEK 2 COMPACT.

Result: 2213 blood cultures were collected from suspected sepsis patients in ICUs. Out of these, 970 (43%) were positive and among them *Candida* spp. was isolated in 76 (7.8%). Out of these 76 (7.8%) specimens, isolation rate of *Candida albicans* was 17% while 83% being *Candida non-albicans*. Among *Candida albicans*, we found that, resistance rate to fluconazole was 23% while with voriconazole its 46%. Among *Candida non-albican* highest resistance was seen with fluconazole whereas Flucytosine, Caspofungin, and Micafungin showed highest sensitivity.

Conclusion: The study found that prevalence of candidemia was 7.8%. Isolation rate of *Candida non albicans* was higher as compared to *Candida albicans*. *Candida albicans* and non *albicans* showed highest resistance to azole group, but sensitive to echinocandins group. Accurate identification of *Candida* species and their antifungal resistance is crucial for early intervention, personalized treatment, and improved patient outcomes.

Keywords: Candidemia, *Candida albicans*, *Candida non albicans*, antifungal agents, Fluconazole, Voriconazole, Echinocandins.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Invasive candidiasis refers to invasive fungal disease which is caused by haematogenous spread of *Candida* spp. (also known as candidemia) to the internal organs.[1] In hospitalized patients, invasive candidiasis is the most prevalent type. Approximately 96% of opportunistic mycoses are caused by *Candida*, which is also a major contributor to bloodstream infections (BSI).[2,3] Human skin and mucosa naturally harbour *Candida* spp., but due to risk factors like overuse of antibiotics, cancers, HIV infection, organ transplantation, extended hospital stays, and exposure to invasive procedures,

these pathogens have been reported more frequently.[4] *Candida* infections result from an intricate interplay between fungal virulence and host immunity. *Candida albicans* uses adhesion molecules, enzymes, hyphae formation, and contact sensing to colonize and penetrate epithelial surfaces. Its dynamic regulation of virulence factors and rapid adaptability enable evasion of host defences, facilitating infection.[5] According to model calculations, the annual incidence of candidemia in India is projected to be 1,88,355. However, the researchers claim that the true yearly incidence of can-

didemia is closer to 470,000 cases due to the limited sensitivity of blood cultures for diagnosing invasive candidiasis. About 42% of cases are most likely caused by *Candida tropicalis*, with estimated cases caused by *Candida albicans* and *Candida auris* being 21% and 5.3%, respectively.[6] Global health is currently deemed threatened by the newly discovered pathogen *Candida auris*. Due to its resistance to fluconazole, and decreased susceptibility to other triazole antifungals. The majority of strains of *Candida auris* are considered multi drug-resistant because of the high rates of treatment failure and mortality linked to invasive infections. Furthermore, *Candida auris*'s environmental persistence and resistance to conventional disinfectants increase the probability of an epidemic.[7] So our study aimed to find incidence of candidemia, prevalence of predominant fungal species and its anti-fungal resistance pattern in ICUs of a multi-speciality hospital, Gujarat.

Objectives:

- To know the Prevalence of Invasive candidiasis in Blood stream infection
- To know the prevalence of predominant fungal species in candidemia
- To know antifungal resistance pattern in invasive Candidiasis.

Methodology

The data for microbiological assessment for invasive candidiasis in blood stream infection was analysed from 1st May, 2022 to 30th April, 2024 for the patients from ICU, Multi-Speciality hospital, Gujarat.

[Process which was followed in Microbiology Laboratory for processing blood culture bottle: After receiving blood culture bottles in Microbiology Laboratory, Blood culture bottles were loaded in BACT/ALERT 3D machine for 5 days of aerobic incubation then after positive blood culture bottles were subjected to Gram stain as well as for culture Nutrient agar and SDA (Sabouraud Dextrose Agar), In Gram staining, *Candida* species

were identified. Then after 48 hours of incubation at 37° C, growth of organisms was identified by Gram stain. Germ tube test was performed for conforming *Candida albicans* and *Candida non albicans*; identification and antifungal susceptibility pattern was done in automated system VITEK 2 COMPACT and also identification was confirmed by chromogenic media for colour identification of sub species.

Preparation of inoculation for Vitek 2 ID/AST System:

1. Inoculums was prepared by picking five-seven distinct colonies of approximately 1mm from 48 hours old culture grown on Saboteur Dextrose Agar and incubated at 35 ± 2°C. Colonies was suspended in 3ml of sterile 0.85% Saline.
2. Vortex the resulting suspension and adjust the turbidity to yield 1 x 10⁶ to 5 x 10⁶ cells /ml (i.e.1.8 to 2.2 McFarland standard) -Tube no 1.
3. Transferred 280µl inoculated suspension from tube no1 to tube no2 which contain 3ml of sterile normal saline, which was placed in Vitek 2 cassette along with a sterile polystyrene test tube and the AST-YS08 card containing serial dilutions of each anti-fungal agent was tested.

Vitek 2 microbial ID/AST testing system method: Susceptibility of *Candida* spp. isolates to each anti-fungal agent was determined by utilizing the AST-YS08 cards containing the anti-fungal agents Amphotericin B, Capsosfungin, Micafungin, Flucytosine, Fluconazole and Voriconazole.

Result

Over the course of the two-year investigation, our centre collected 2213 blood culture from suspected sepsis patients from ICUs; Out of these, 970(43 %) blood culture specimens was positive. Out of 970 blood culture positive specimens, *Candida* spp. was isolated in 76 (7.8%) blood culture specimens.

Distribution of isolation of *Candida* spp has been mentioned in Table 1.

Table 1: The distribution of candidemia in ICUs patients:

Distribution of <i>Candida</i> spp.		
Gender wise positivity rate [n= 76]		
Male	53	76 %
Female	23	24 %
ICU Wise positivity rate[n= 76]		
NICU	7	9 %
PICU	13	17 %
ADULT ICU	56	74 %
Age wise positivity rate[n= 76]		
<18	14	18 %
18-60	52	68 %
>60	10	14 %

The *Candida* spp. was identified by microscopically and based on growth on SDA. After that the germ tube test was performed and 13(17%) isolates showed positive results. [Table 2, figure 1].

Table 2: Differentiation of *Candida albicans* and *Candida non albicans* based on Germ tube test.

Germ tube test	Positive	Negative
Total 76 isolates	13 (17%)	63(83%)

Figure 1: Germ – tube test

All the isolates were identified by use of VITEK 2 COMPACT automated machine and also identified by use of chromogenic *Candida* HiChrome agar which was shown in Table 3 and Figure 2.

Candida spp. was identified in 76 blood culture specimens among them 13 (17%) were *Candida*

albicans, whereas 64 (83%) were *Candida non-albicans*.

Among *Candida non albicans*, *Candida tropicalis* (n=26, 34%) mostly commonly isolated followed by *Candida glabrata*, and *Candida parapsilosis*. *Candida auris* was isolated in 2 blood culture bottles.

Table 3: *Candida* spp identification by Vitek 2 compact and Color produced on hiChrome agar

Identified by Vitek 2 Compact	Isolates (n = 76)	Color produced on Chrome agar
<i>Candida albicans</i>	13(17%)	Green color
<i>Candida parapsilosis</i>	14(18%)	Pink color
<i>Candida glabrata</i>	15(20%)	White color
<i>Candida tropicalis</i>	26(34%)	Metallic blue color
<i>Candida krusei</i>	6 (8%)	Pink color
<i>Candida auris</i>	2 (3%)	White color

Figure 2: Colour production on HI Chrome agar.

Antifungal susceptibility was done in VITEK 2 COMPACT as result mentioned in Table 4. *Candida albicans* showed highest resistance to voriconazole 46% and fluconazole 23%. *Candida non albicans* were mostly sensitive to echinocandins except *Candida glabrata* which showed highest resistance to Capsosungin.

Table 4: *Candida* spp antifungal resistance pattern by Vitek 2 compact

Anti-fungal susceptibility pattern in <i>Candida</i> spp.													
Isolates	No. of total isolates	AB		CAS		FCT		FLU		MCF		VRC	
		R	R (%)	R	R (%)	R	R (%)	R	R (%)	R	R (%)	R	R (%)
<i>Candida albicans</i>	13	5	38	1	8	0	0	3	23	1	8	6	46
<i>Candida glabrata</i>	15	8	53	10	67	2	13	15	100	7	47	5	33
<i>Candida krusei</i>	6	3	50	0	0	6	100	-	-	0	0	0	0
<i>Candida parapsilosis</i>	14	5	35	1	7	2	14	11	73	1	7	9	60
<i>Candida tropicalis</i>	26	3	11	4	15	5	19	8	30	3	11	5	19
<i>Candida auris</i>	2												

R- Resistance, AB- Amphotericin B, CAS- Capsosungin, FCT- Flucytosin, FLU- Fluconazole, MCF Micfungin, VRC- Voriconazole.

Discussion

This research investigated the epidemiological patterns and characteristics of Candidemia cases at a multi-specialty hospital in Gujarat, providing valuable insights into current trends. A consistent upward trend in candidemia cases was detected over the 2-year period spanning May 2022 to April 2024. Analysis of 2,213 blood cultures from ICU patients with suspected sepsis revealed prevalence rate of a *Candida* spp. was 7.8% (n=76). Similar findings were made by H Kaur et al [10] with 1.31% prevalence rate, Rudra Murthy S. M et al [11] reported 5.3% in 2020. Xess et al [14] found a incidence rate of 6% for Candidemia, Verma AK et

al [19] reported an incidence rate of 1.61%, and Kumar CP et al [18] from South India reported an incidence of 5.7%. In a study at Moulana Azad Medical College in New Delhi, India, Sahin V et al [20] found an incidence rate of 6.9% for *Candida* spp. Candidemia occurs more frequently in ICUs than in general wards due to factors such as underlying health conditions, invasive procedures, medical devices, and broad-spectrum antibiotic use, which foster *Candida* colonization and invasive candidiasis. [8,9]

In our study we found that males have higher prevalence (76%) of candidemia compare to females (24%). Rajni E et al [2] reported

candidemia in males were 66.3% while in females it was 33.7%. While Bhattacharya P et al [4] al reported females have higher rate of candidemia in compare to males. Most of the cases of candidemia came from adult ICU followed by paediatric ICU. Which was same reported by Bhattacharya P et al [4] and Rajni E et al [2] in which most common age group was between 18-60 years of age group which was same observed in our study.

In our study we found that isolation rate of *Candida non albicans* were higher, among them *Candida tropicalis* was the most often isolated *Candida* species, the same was 40.1% reported by H. Kaur et al[10] and 24.28%. Bhattacharjee P et al [10]. Due to broad spectrum usage of Antibiotics and longer hospital stay, immunocompromised state, prevalence of *non albicans* is higher.

In our data analysis, The antifungal susceptibility testing revealed that 46% of *Candida albicans* isolates exhibited resistance to voriconazole, whereas 23% demonstrated resistance to fluconazole, which was nearly observed by H. Kaur et al 7.8 % [10], whereas Sridharan S et al [22] and Piqueras, A et al[23] showed all isolates of *Candida albican* were susceptible to Fluconazole.

In present study, we observed an alarming rise in antifungal resistance, particularly to azole-based medications, in *Candida non-albicans* species. This finding was consistent with previous research by K.E. Pristov et al [13], Xiang et al [15], and Zomorodian et al [16]. It is uncommon for *Candida non albicans* to be resistant to Echinocandins (capsfungin and micafungin) but *Candida glabrata* showed highest resistance to capsfungin 67% which was comparable with Perlin DS. et al [17] and resistance to micafungin 47% which was comparable with Piqueras A et al[23].

Candidemia remains a significant cause of morbidity and mortality. The changing patterns of its epidemiology and the rising resistance to antifungal treatments highlight the critical need for continuous surveillance of these cases.

Conclusion:

Changes in epidemiology and the increasing prevalence rates of candidemia underscore the importance of accurate detection of *Candida* species. Our study found 7.8% incidence rate of candidemia in ICU of a multi-speciality hospital, Gujarat, with *Candida albicans* isolated in 17% of cases and *non-albicans* in 83%. *Candida tropicalis* and *Candida glabrata* were the most common prevalent organisms. *Candida albicans* showed 46% resistance to voriconazole and 23% to fluconazole. *Candida non-albicans* were largely susceptible to Flucytosine, Capsfungin, and Micafungin, except *Candida glabrata*, which was resistant to fluconazole and Capsfungin. Prompt

identification of *Candida* species and their antifungal resistance is essential for ICU patients, facilitating early intervention and personalized treatment, and improving patient outcomes.

Reference:

- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Invasive Candidiasis (<https://www.cdc.gov/fungal/diseases/candidiasis/invasive/index.html#:~:text=Invasive%20candidiasis%20is%20an%20infection,other%20parts%20of%20the%20body.>). Accessed 1/27/2022.
- Rajni E, Chaudhary P, Garg VK, Sharma R, Malik M. A complete clinico-epidemiological and microbiological profile of candidemia cases in a tertiary-care hospital in Western India. *Antimicrobial Stewardship & Healthcare Epidemiology*. 2022; 2(1):e37. doi:10.1017/ash.2021.235
- Wisplinghoff H, Bischoff T, Tallent SM, Seifert H, Wenzel RP, Edmond MB. Nosocomial bloodstream infections in US hospitals: Analysis of 24,179 cases from a prospective nationwide surveillance study. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2004; 39:309–17
- Bhattacharjee P. Epidemiology and antifungal susceptibility of *Candida* species in a tertiary care hospital, Kolkata, India. *Curr Med Mycol*. 2016 Jun; 2(2):20-27. doi: 10.18869/acadpub.Cmm.2.2.5. PMID: 28681016; PMCID: PMC5490301.
- Odds, F. C. (1994). Pathogenesis of *Candida* infections. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology*, 31(3), S2–S5. doi:10.1016/s0190-9622(08)81257-1
- Animesh Ray, Adarsh Aayilliath K, Sayantan Banerjee, Arunaloke Chakrabarti, David W Denning, Burden of Serious Fungal Infections in India, *Open Forum Infectious Diseases*, Volume 9, Issue 12, December 2022
- Levy Y, Miltgen G, Rousseau A, Lugagne N, Teyssyre L, Traversier N, Desnos-Ollivier M, Allou N, Allyn J. Case Report: Emergence of *Candida auris* in the Indian Ocean Region. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*. 2020 Dec 14; 104(2):739-743. doi: 10.4269/ajtmh.20-0758. PMID: 33319729; PMCID: PMC7866352.
- Cuenca-Estrella M, Gomez-Lopez A, Alastruey- Izquierdo A, Bernal-Martinez L, Cuesta I, Buitrago MJ, et al. Comparison of the Vitek 2 antifungal susceptibility system with the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) and European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) broth microdilution reference methods and with the Sensititre Yeast One and Etest techniques for in vitro detection of antifungal resistance in yeast isolates. *J Clin Microbiol*. 2010.

9. Alfouzan W, Al-Enezi T, AlRoomi E, Sandhya V, Chandy R, Khan ZU. Comparison of the VITEK 2 antifungal susceptibility system with Etest using clinical isolates of *Candida* species. *Rev Iberoam Micol.* 2017 Jul-Sep; 34(3):171-174. doi: 10.1016/j.riam.2016.12.002. Epub 2017 Jun 13. PMID: 28622982.
10. Kaur H, Singh S, Rudramurthy S, Ghosh A, Jayashree M, and Narayana Y, et al. *Candida* emia in a tertiary care centre of developing country: monitoring possible change in spectrum of agents and antifungal susceptibility. *Indian J Med Microbiol.* 2020; 38:109–15. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijmm.IJMM_20_112.
11. Rudramurthy SM, Chakrabarti A, Paul RA, et al. *Candida auris* *Candida* emia in Indian ICUs: analysis of risk factors. *J Antimicrob Chemother* 2017; 72:1794–1801. [DOI] [Pub Med] [
12. Bhattacharjee P. Epidemiology and antifungal susceptibility of *Candida* species in a tertiary care hospital, Kolkata, India. *Curr Med Mycol.* 2016; 2(2): 20-27. DOI: 10.18869/acadpub.cmm.2.2.5
13. K.E. Pristov, M.A. Ghannoum, Resistance of *Candida* to azoles and echinocandins worldwide, *Clinical Microbiology and Infection*:2019, 25(7),792-798
14. Xess I, Jain N, Hasan F, Mandal P, Banerjee U. Epidemiology of candidemia in a tertiary care centre of north India: 5-year study. *Infection.* 2007; 35(4):256-9
15. Xiang, G.-S.; Zeng, L.-B.; Zhang, J.-Y.; Ying, Y.; Deng, X.- R.; Hu, X.-F.; Yan, Y.; Yu, K.-H.; Zou, W.-W.; Huang, X.- T. J. J. J. o. M. In Vitro Antidrug Susceptibility Testing of *Candida* Species Isolated from Aseptic Body Fluids. 2018, 11.
16. Zomorodian, K.; Bandegani, A.; Mirhendi, H.; Pakshir, K.; Alinejhad, N.; Fard, A. P. J. J. j. o. m. In vitro susceptibility and trailing growth effect of clinical isolates of *Candida* species to azole drugs. 2016, 9.
17. Perlin DS. Echinocandin Resistance in *Candida* . *Clin Infect Dis.* 2015 Dec 1; 61 Suppl 6(Suppl 6): S612-7. doi: 10.1093/cid/civ791. PMID: 26567278; PMCID: PMC4643482.
18. Kumar CP, Sundarajan T, Menon T, Venkatadesikal M. Candidosis in children with onco-hematological studies in Chennai, South India. *Jpn J Infect Dis.* 2005; 58(4):218-21.
19. Verma AK, Prasad KN, Singh M, Dixit AK, Ayyagari A. *Candida* emia in patients of a tertiary health care hospital from north India. *Indian J Med Res.* 2003; 117:122-8.
20. Sahni V, Agarwal SK, Singh NP, Anuradha S, Sikdar S, Wadhwa A, et al. Candidemia-an under- recognized nosocomial infection in Indian hospitals. *J Assoc Physicians India.* 2005; 53:607-11.
21. Rajkumari N, Mathur P, Xess I, Misra MC. Distribution of different yeasts isolates among trauma patients and comparison of accuracy in identification of yeasts by automated method versus conventional methods for better use in low resource countries. *Indian J Med Microbiol.* 2014; 32(4):391-7.
22. Sridharan S, Gopalakrishnan R, Nambi PS, Kumar S, Sethuraman N, Ramasubramanian V. *Indian J Crit Care Med* 2021;25(3):267–272.
23. Piqueras, A.; Ganapathi, L.; Carpenter, J.F.; Rubio, T.; Sandora, T.J.; Flett, K.B.; Köhler, J.R. Trends in Pediatric Candidemia: Epidemiology, Anti-Fungal Susceptibility, and Patient Characteristics in a Children’s Hospital. *J. Fungi* 2021, 7, 78. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof7020078>.